

Variation of n-Alkanes in Surface Wax of Leaves of *Ocimum sanctum*

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ANALYSIS of essential oil of leaves of sacred basil, *Ocimum sanctum* (Fam.: Labiatae) is well documented¹⁻³. But no chemical analysis has yet been done on the surface lipids of leaves of *O. sanctum* although it is a well known fact that the surface lipids play a vital role in affecting transpiration and leaf surface properties since the surface lipid composition may vary with environmental situation as well as with the age of the plant⁴⁻⁶. Somewhere it was felt that composition of plant surface lipids and particularly alkane distribution of surface wax might be used in chemotaxonomy⁷⁻¹⁰. As a part of our study on the distribution of surface lipids of leaves of *O. sanctum* at various stages of the plant throughout a year, the present note deals with the characterisation and the variation of surface hydrocarbons, mainly n-alkanes.

Surface wax was extracted in cold hexane (analytical grade) in the usual way from the fresh leaves collected at the months (1982-83) of some important stages of the plant, e.g. July (young stage; plants grown in June), September (pre-influrescence), November, December (flowering), January (post-flowering), March (maximum seed maturing) and May (dying). The crude extract in each case was fractionated through preparative tlc with CCl₄ as a chromatographic solvent. The hydrocarbon band

was identified through co-tlc studies with standard paraffins. The eluted band showed no carbonyl absorption in the infrared region and the absence of alkene was confirmed through argentometric tlc¹¹. The purified hydrocarbon fraction was analysed directly by a programmed glc run (temp., 170-300° at 5° min⁻¹; initial period 1 min and final 15 mins) on a 10% SE-30 glass column (2m×1/8" i.d.) with flame ionisation detector, and characterised through co-glc run with authentic samples of n-alkanes (Sigma). The analyses of hydrocarbons present in cuticular wax of leaves of the plant at various stages are presented in Table 1.

The analyses revealed the presence of all the members of n-alkane in the series C₁₆–C₂₇ at all the said stages of the plant and none of these n-alkanes have previously been reported to be present in the leaves of *O. sanctum*. The major n-alkanes were present at most of the referred stages in the range C₂₀–C₂₅ (usual for plant surface hydrocarbons¹⁰) of which C₂₃ and C₂₅ (less usual⁷) were most dominating. In the last half of flowering stage (December) these two dominating n-alkanes (n-C₂₃ and C₂₅) were minimum in comparison to their relative occurrences in rest of the said stages. Since there was a marked divergence in the exhibited leaf hydrocarbon distribution pattern of *O. sanctum* at various stages, but it was a interesting trend to note that the relative proportions of n-alkanes which decreased in December again increased in January (post-flowering stage), e.g. n-C₁₆–C₁₈, C₂₀, C₂₁ and C₂₃–C₂₇, and just opposite observation appeared in the members of n-alkanes in the range C₂₁–C₂₆ and the only exceptions were C₁₆ and C₂₂. The composition ratio of odd members to

TABLE 1—MONTHLY VARIATION OF HYDROCARBON CONSTITUENTS (mol %) OF LEAF WAX OF *Ocimum sanctum*

Carbon No. of n-alkanes	July	September	November	December	January	March	May
C ₁₆	0.12	0.09	2.68	0.08	1.74	0.62	0.17
C ₁₇	0.09	0.13	0.90	0.04	0.23	2.49	0.18
C ₁₈	0.80	0.98	2.77	0.22	1.61	6.51	0.40
C ₁₉	0.26	0.25	1.48	0.44	0.06	3.70	0.29
C ₂₀	0.44	0.55	1.42	0.59	0.91	0.97	0.58
C ₂₁	0.49	0.20	0.11	0.83	0.06	1.52	1.07
C ₂₂	0.95	0.38	0.54	2.25	0.29	0.18	2.51
C ₂₃	1.27	0.32	0.22	4.23	0.15	0.29	3.54
C ₂₄	1.17	0.43	0.30	5.90	0.16	0.58	3.18
C ₂₅	0.85	1.58	0.25	7.12	0.29	0.96	2.37
C ₂₆	0.68	0.54	0.31	5.71	0.34	0.40	1.61
C ₂₇	0.92	0.74	0.62	5.60	1.08	0.96	1.78
C ₂₈	0.53	0.61	0.51	5.14	0.41	0.54	0.95
C ₂₉	2.05	2.20	2.34	5.83	4.77	3.07	3.02
C ₃₀	1.71	1.56	1.88	4.96	2.17	2.12	1.91
C ₃₁	9.19	8.12	8.16	7.23	11.60	6.55	8.22
C ₃₂	2.53	2.57	2.02	3.05	3.51	2.18	2.57
C ₃₃	18.28	25.73	31.86	14.08	29.53	22.52	21.92
C ₃₄	7.62	5.20	4.20	3.78	6.53	5.59	4.78
C ₃₅	23.85	27.10	23.93	13.58	13.33	19.13	20.85
C ₃₆	5.45	4.08	0.55	0.40	3.17	3.76	2.07
C ₃₇	0.73	3.09	2.30	0.95	2.81	1.80	1.95
Branched chain alkanes	20.52	14.20	11.75	8.59	10.28	14.16	14.13
Composition ratio of odd members to total n-alkanes	57.99	69.44	71.59	59.94	68.90	63.00	65.15

total n-alkanes was maximum in November and minimum in July (young stage) with two sharp decrease in December and March (maximum seed maturing stage).

The occurrence of branched hydrocarbon as minor components (common expectation for higher plants^{1,2}) in all the said stages, was minimum in December and maximum in July (young stage).

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References

1. B. M. LAWRENCE, J. W. HOGG, S. J. TERHUNE and N. PICHITAKUL, *Flavour Ind.*, 1972, 3, 47.
2. R. N. LAL, T. K. SEN and M. C. NIGAM, *Perfuem. Kosmet.*, 1978, 59, 230.
3. S. DUTT, *Indian Soap J.*, 1940, 6, 248.
4. R. HARDMAN, C. N. WOOD and E. A. SOFOWARA, *Phytochemistry*, 1970, 9, 1087.
5. G. A. HERBIN and P. A. ROBINS, *Phytochemistry*, 1969, 8, 1985.
6. J. L. HARWOOD and P. K. STUMPF, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1971, 142, 281.
7. J. B. DEL CASTILLO, C. J. W. BROOKS, R. C. CAMBIE, G. EGLINTON, R. J. HAMILTON and P. PELLITI, *Phytochemistry*, 1967, 6, 391.
8. R. O. MARTIN, G. SUBRAMANIAN and H. E. CONNER, *Phytochemistry*, 1967, 6, 559.
9. W. G. DYSON and G. A. HERBIN, *Phytochemistry*, 1970, 9, 585.
10. G. EGLINTON and R. J. HAMILTON in "Chemical Plant Taxonomy", ed. T. SWAIN, Academic Press, New York, 1963, p. 187.
11. V. MAHADEVAN, *Lipids*, 1967, 1, 195.
12. P. E. KOLATTUKUDY and T. J. WALTON, *Prog. Chem. Fats Lipids*, 1972, 13, 143.